

Train What, Not Where:

An Empirical Study of BatchNorm-Only Fine-Tuning for Fine-Grained Visual Classification

HyonHeum Cho
Department of Computer Engineering
Gachon University, South Korea
edwin12628@gachon.ac.kr
<https://github.com/Edwin-Cho>

Abstract

*Transfer learning via fine-tuning pre-trained convolutional neural networks is the dominant paradigm for visual classification tasks. However, conventional fine-tuning strategies focus on which layers to unfreeze (position-based selection), leaving the question of which layer types to train largely unexplored in the context of resource-constrained, fine-grained classification. In this work, we present a systematic empirical study of **BatchNorm-only (BN-only) fine-tuning**, where only Batch Normalization layers are trainable while all convolutional filters remain frozen. Using ResNet-50 on a 122-breed dog classification dataset derived from **Stanford Dogs** (20,753 images), we show that BN-only fine-tuning achieves **73.50%** validation accuracy—matching or exceeding full fine-tuning (73.40%, $\Delta = +0.10$ pp)—while reducing trainable parameters by **95.3%** (from 24.7M to 1.2M). Notably, BN-only fine-tuning exhibits a near-zero train-validation gap of **+0.6%** compared to **+23.7%** for full fine-tuning, demonstrating strong implicit regularization. We introduce a Parameter-Normalized Accuracy (PNA) metric and show a **20×** improvement over full fine-tuning, with estimated GPU memory savings of **62%** and **33%** faster training. Our findings suggest that type-based parameter selection offers a practical and effective alternative for fine-grained classification under resource constraints. Code is available at <https://github.com/Edwin-Cho/Fine-Grained-Dog-Classification>.*

1 Introduction

Fine-grained visual classification (FGVC)—distinguishing visually similar subcategories such as dog breeds, bird species, or car models—remains a challenging task due to subtle inter-class differences and large intra-class variation [Khosla et al., 2011]. Transfer learning from ImageNet-pretrained models [Deng et al., 2009, Kornblith et al., 2019] has become the standard approach, with *fine-tuning* as the predominant adaptation strategy.

The conventional fine-tuning paradigm is **position-based**: practitioners choose a layer index and unfreeze all layers above it, implicitly assuming that deeper layers encode more task-specific features. While effective, this strategy incurs substantial computational cost. For ResNet-50 [He et al., 2016], full fine-tuning trains 24.7M parameters, typically requiring around 8 GB GPU memory and several hours of training on a single modern GPU. Such requirements present a significant barrier for researchers and practitioners operating under resource constraints—e.g., consumer-grade GPUs (≤ 4 GB VRAM), free-tier cloud instances, or edge devices.

An alternative perspective, which we term **type-based selection**, asks: “Which layer types should be trained?” rather than “Which layers should be unfrozen?” This

shift in framing leads naturally to Batch Normalization (BN) [Ioffe and Szegedy, 2015] as a fine-tuning target. BN layers contain domain-specific statistics (running mean μ , variance σ^2) and learnable affine parameters (scale γ , shift β) that mediate the distribution of intermediate activations. When transferring from a source domain (ImageNet) to a target domain (dog breeds), adapting these statistics may suffice if the convolutional filters already capture generalizable low- and mid-level features.

Several prior works have touched upon training BN parameters in transfer settings. Li et al. [2016] proposed Adaptive BN (AdaBN) for domain adaptation; Frankle et al. [2021] demonstrated that randomly initialized CNNs can achieve non-trivial accuracy by training only BN layers; Kanavati and Tsuneki [2021] studied BN expressiveness in medical imaging transfer; and Yazdanpanah et al. [2022] revisited BN affines in few-shot learning. However, a systematic empirical analysis of BN-only fine-tuning for *fine-grained* classification under *resource-constrained* settings—with quantitative efficiency metrics and overfitting characterization—has not been systematically explored. Rather than introducing a new architectural module, this work reframes selective fine-tuning as a **type-based adaptation problem** and investigates its practical implications for resource-constrained fine-grained recogni-

tion.

Contributions.

This paper makes the following contributions:

1. A **systematic empirical study** of BN-only fine-tuning for fine-grained visual classification on a Stanford Dogs-based dataset (122 breeds), providing controlled comparisons against full fine-tuning and a head-only ablation baseline under identical training configurations.
2. **Quantitative evidence** that type-based selective fine-tuning can match the accuracy of conventional full fine-tuning while substantially improving generalization under limited data. In our ResNet-50 experiments, BN-only fine-tuning attains 73.50% validation accuracy vs. 73.40% for full fine-tuning ($\Delta = +0.10$ percentage points), while reducing the number of trainable parameters by 95.3% and shrinking the train-validation gap from +23.7% to +0.6%.
3. A **Parameter-Normalized Accuracy (PNA)** metric—defined as the ratio of validation accuracy to the number of trainable parameters (in millions)—for lightweight comparison of parameter-efficient transfer strategies. BN-only fine-tuning achieves a roughly $20\times$ higher PNA than full fine-tuning, along with estimated resource savings of about 62% in GPU memory usage and 33% in training time.

2 Related Work

2.1 Transfer Learning and Fine-Tuning Strategies

Transfer learning from ImageNet-pretrained models is the de facto standard for visual recognition [Kornblith et al., 2019]. Fine-tuning strategies vary along a spectrum: from training only a linear classification head (*feature extraction*) to updating all network parameters (*full fine-tuning*), with intermediate approaches that unfreeze the top- k layers. These strategies are fundamentally *position-based*—the selection criterion is the layer’s ordinal position in the network. Our work proposes an orthogonal axis: *type-based* selection, where the criterion is the layer’s functional role (e.g., normalization vs. convolution).

2.2 Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning

The growing scale of deep models has spurred interest in parameter-efficient fine-tuning (PEFT) methods. LoRA [Hu et al., 2022] introduces low-rank decomposition of weight updates; BitFit [Zaken et al., 2022] trains only bias terms in Transformer models; and adapter modules [Mudrakarta et al., 2019] insert lightweight trainable bottleneck layers. While these methods target language

models or Transformers, BN-only fine-tuning addresses a complementary niche: CNN-based visual classification where BN layers serve as natural domain adaptation interfaces.

2.3 Batch Normalization in Transfer Learning

Li et al. [2016] introduced Adaptive BN (AdaBN), which replaces source-domain BN statistics with target-domain statistics for domain adaptation, without learning any parameters. Frankle et al. [2021] demonstrated that training *only* BN layers in randomly initialized networks yields surprisingly competitive accuracy, revealing the expressive power of BN affines. Kanavati and Tsuneki [2021] studied BN parameter training for medical imaging transfer, showing that BN-only models can approach full fine-tuning performance in pathology tasks. Yazdanpanah et al. [2022] revisited BN affine learning in the context of few-shot transfer learning, demonstrating benefits in low-data regimes.

Our work differs from these studies in several key aspects: **(i)** we focus on *fine-grained* natural image classification (122 dog breeds), a setting with high inter-class similarity not addressed by prior BN transfer studies; **(ii)** we provide a *systematic efficiency analysis* including parameter count, training time, estimated memory usage, and a unified Parameter-Normalized Accuracy (PNA); **(iii)** we characterize the *implicit regularization* effect through train-validation gap analysis, showing that BN-only fine-tuning effectively prevents overfitting—a critical concern for fine-grained datasets with limited samples per class.

3 Method

3.1 Problem Setting

We consider fine-grained visual classification with C classes, where a pre-trained backbone f_θ (ResNet-50, trained on ImageNet) is adapted to a target dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ with limited computational resources. The goal is to maximize classification accuracy while minimizing the number of trainable parameters and associated resource consumption.

3.2 BN-Only Fine-Tuning Strategy

Batch Normalization Recap. For an input activation x in a mini-batch \mathcal{B} , BN computes:

$$\text{BN}(x) = \gamma \cdot \frac{x - \mu_{\mathcal{B}}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2 + \epsilon}} + \beta \quad (1)$$

where $\mu_{\mathcal{B}}$ and $\sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2$ are the batch statistics, and γ (scale) and β (shift) are learnable affine parameters. During inference, running estimates of mean and variance replace batch statistics.

Type-Based Selection. In contrast to position-based fine-tuning (unfreezing layers above index k), we propose *type-based* selection:

$$\text{trainable}(\ell) = \begin{cases} \text{True} & \text{if } \ell \in \{\text{BatchNorm layers}\} \\ \text{True} & \text{if } \ell \in \{\text{Classification head}\} \\ \text{False} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

This freezes all convolutional filters (which encode general-purpose visual features learned from ImageNet) while allowing BN layers to adapt the feature distribution statistics to the target domain.

Theoretical Motivation. The key hypothesis is that the domain gap between ImageNet and a fine-grained target domain (e.g., dog breeds) primarily manifests as a *distributional shift* in intermediate feature activations, rather than a fundamental deficiency in the extracted features themselves. Convolutional filters trained on ImageNet capture edges, textures, and shapes that are broadly useful for natural images. By updating only the BN affine parameters (γ, β) and the running statistics (μ, σ^2), the model can re-calibrate activation distributions without disturbing the learned feature extractors.

3.3 Architecture

We use ResNet-50 [He et al., 2016] as the backbone, with the original classification head replaced by a custom head:

$$\text{ResNet50} \rightarrow \text{GAP} \rightarrow \text{BN} \rightarrow \text{Dropout}(0.5) \rightarrow \text{Dense}(512) \rightarrow \text{BN} \rightarrow \text{Dropout}(0.3) \rightarrow \text{Dense}(C)$$

where GAP denotes Global Average Pooling and $C = 122$ is the number of dog breeds. The ResNet-50 backbone contains 53 BN layers; together with the 2 BN layers in the classification head, this yields 1.2M trainable parameters out of 24.7M total (4.7%). Figure 1 illustrates the architecture and parameter distribution.

3.4 Parameter-Normalized Accuracy (PNA)

To provide a lightweight comparison metric, we define *Parameter-Normalized Accuracy* (PNA) as:

$$\text{PNA} = \frac{\text{Validation Accuracy (\%)}}{\text{Trainable Parameters (millions)}} \quad (3)$$

A higher PNA indicates better accuracy per unit of trainable capacity. This metric is intended as a lightweight comparative heuristic rather than a comprehensive systems benchmark; it does not account for inference FLOPs, forward/backward latency, or device-level memory profiling. Within these constraints, PNA captures the parameter-accuracy trade-off analogously to FLOPs-normalized accuracy in architecture search literature.

Figure 1: BN-only fine-tuning architecture. Convolutional layers (blue, frozen) retain ImageNet features, while Batch-Norm layers (red, trainable) adapt activation distributions to the target domain. The classification head is fully trainable.

4 Experiments

4.1 Dataset

We build on the Stanford Dogs dataset [Khosla et al., 2011], which originally contains 20,580 images of 120 dog breeds. For our experiments, we extend this dataset by adding two additional Korean dog breeds, resulting in a 122-class dataset with 20,753 images in total. We adopt an 80/20 train/validation split, yielding 16,647 training and 4,106 validation images. Data augmentation includes random rotation ($\pm 20^\circ$), width/height shift (0.2), zoom (0.2), shear (0.2), and horizontal flip. Validation images are only rescaled (no augmentation).

4.2 Training Configuration

Both BN-only and full fine-tuning experiments use identical configurations to ensure a fair comparison:

- **Optimizer:** Adam with initial learning rate 10^{-4}
- **Loss:** Categorical cross-entropy
- **Batch size:** 32
- **Epochs:** 35
- **Early stopping:** patience = 10, restoring best weights
- **Learning rate schedule:** ReduceLROnPlateau (factor = 0.5, patience = 5, min LR = 10^{-7})
- **Hardware:** Apple M4 Pro GPU

The only difference between conditions is the set of trainable parameters: BN-only fine-tuning trains 1.2M parameters (4.7% of total), while full fine-tuning trains 24.7M parameters (99.8%).

4.3 Main Results

Table 1 summarizes the comparison between BN-only and full fine-tuning on our 122-class dog breed dataset. As shown in Table 1, BN-only fine-tuning achieves 73.50% validation accuracy, slightly *exceeding* full fine-tuning (73.40%, $\Delta = +0.10$ pp).

Table 1: BN-only vs. full fine-tuning on a Stanford Dogs-based dataset (122 breeds). PNA = Parameter-Normalized Accuracy, defined in Equation (3). GPU memory is estimated based on optimizer state size.

Metric	BN-Only	Full FT
Trainable Params	1.2M (4.7%)	24.7M (99.8%)
Best Val. Accuracy	73.50%	73.40%
Final Train Accuracy	73.85%	97.1%
Train-Val Gap	+0.6%	+23.7%
PNA (Acc / M params)	62.9	3.0
Training Time	2.7 h	4.0 h
Est. GPU Memory	~3 GB	~8 GB

Given a standard error estimate of $SE \approx 0.69\%$ (based on $n = 4,106$ validation samples and per-class accuracy variance), this difference falls within one standard error, suggesting that the two methods achieve statistically equivalent performance. The PNA for BN-only is 62.9, a $20\times$ improvement over full fine-tuning (3.0), indicating dramatically better accuracy per trainable parameter.

4.4 Ablation: Trainable Parameter Set

To isolate the contribution of BN layers from that of the classification head, we compare three fine-tuning strategies: (i) **Head-Only**, where only the GAP + BN + Dense classification head is trained while the entire ResNet-50 backbone remains frozen (~ 1.1 M params); (ii) **BN-Only (Ours)**, where backbone BN layers and the head are jointly trainable (~ 1.2 M params); and (iii) **Full Fine-Tuning**, where all 24.7M parameters are updated.

Figure 2 summarizes the results. Head-Only achieves only 7.06% validation accuracy after 35 epochs, compared to 73.50% for BN-Only—a gap of +66.4 percentage points. Crucially, the two strategies differ by a negligible 0.1M trainable parameters (1.1M vs. 1.2M), confirming that the gain is attributable specifically to BN-layer domain adaptation rather than parameter count alone. BN layers re-calibrate intermediate feature distributions to the target domain, enabling effective reuse of frozen ImageNet features; without this re-calibration, the classification head alone cannot bridge the distribution gap between ImageNet pre-training and fine-grained dog breeds.

Figure 2: Ablation study comparing three fine-tuning strategies: (a) best validation accuracy and (b) trainable parameters. Head-Only and BN-Only share nearly identical parameter counts (~ 1.1 – 1.2 M) yet differ by 66.4 pp in accuracy, isolating the contribution of BN-layer domain adaptation.

4.5 Overfitting Analysis

The most striking finding is the difference in generalization behavior. Full fine-tuning achieves 97.1% training accuracy but only 73.40% validation accuracy, yielding a train-validation gap of +23.7%—a clear signature of overfitting. In contrast, BN-only fine-tuning shows a gap of merely +0.6% (73.85% train vs. 73.26% val at the final epoch), indicating robust generalization without explicit regularization beyond the frozen backbone. Note that for full fine-tuning, the gap is computed between the final epoch’s training accuracy (epoch 24: 97.1%) and the best

validation accuracy (epoch 14: 73.40%), reflecting the worst-case divergence between the two curves.

This implicit regularization arises because frozen convolutional weights drastically limit the model’s effective capacity. The model cannot memorize training samples through convolutional filter adaptation; instead, it can only adjust the activation distributions via BN parameters, which provides a natural bottleneck against overfitting.

Figure 3: BN-only vs. full fine-tuning: (a) validation accuracy and (b) trainable parameters.

Figure 4: BN-only vs. full fine-tuning: (c) train–validation gap and (d) Parameter-Normalized Accuracy (PNA).

4.6 Training Dynamics

Figure 5 shows the training curves for BN-only fine-tuning. The model exhibits rapid initial convergence (epochs 1–5), steady improvement (epochs 6–11), fine-grained adjustment after learning rate reduction (epochs 12–15), and saturation (epochs 16–35). Throughout training, the train–validation accuracy gap remains within 3–5 percentage points, and the loss curve is notably smooth with minimal oscillation—characteristics of stable optimization.

In contrast, Figure 6 shows the full fine-tuning dynamics. Validation accuracy exhibits pronounced oscillation throughout training, with early stopping triggered at epoch 24 (best validation accuracy at epoch 14: 73.40%).

Training accuracy continues rising to 97.1% while validation accuracy plateaus, producing a train–validation gap of +23.7%. The instability and early divergence between the two curves confirm that full fine-tuning is prone to overfitting on this dataset.

Figure 5: BN-only fine-tuning training curves. The train–validation gap remains minimal throughout training, indicating stable convergence without overfitting.

Figure 6: Full fine-tuning training curves (35-epoch budget, early stopping at epoch 24). Validation accuracy oscillates and diverges from training accuracy, indicating overfitting. The dashed vertical line marks the best validation epoch.

4.7 Per-Class Analysis

To assess performance beyond aggregate accuracy, we compute the macro accuracy over the 25 most frequent classes (by training-set count), obtaining 78.76%. This higher figure suggests that BN-only fine-tuning is particularly effective for well-represented classes, while rarer breeds—with as few as ~100 training images—present a greater challenge. Figure 7 shows the normalized confusion matrix for these top-25 classes.

Figure 7: Normalized confusion matrix for the top-25 most frequent classes. Strong diagonal entries indicate reliable classification; off-diagonal confusion is minimal and concentrated among visually similar breeds.

5 Discussion

Why Does BN-Only Fine-Tuning Work? Our results support the hypothesis that the domain gap between ImageNet and fine-grained natural image datasets is primarily distributional rather than representational. ImageNet-trained convolutional filters already encode edges, textures, and shapes that are highly relevant for distinguishing dog breeds. BN layers act as lightweight “adapters” that re-calibrate the mean and variance of feature activations to match the target distribution, while the affine parameters (γ, β) provide additional flexibility for per-channel rescaling and shifting.

Implicit Regularization. The frozen backbone serves as a strong implicit regularizer. With only 4.7% of parameters trainable, the model lacks the capacity to memorize training examples through convolutional weight adaptation. This is empirically confirmed by the small train-validation gap, which indicates that the model generalizes *at least as well* to validation data as it fits training data—a desirable property especially for fine-grained datasets where per-class sample counts are limited (~ 170 images per breed on average).

Practical Implications. BN-only fine-tuning enables training on consumer GPUs with ≤ 4 GB VRAM, requires approximately 33% less training time, and produces models with identical inference cost (the frozen weights are still used at test time; the savings are purely in training). This makes it a practical choice for rapid prototyping, educational settings, and on-device fine-tuning scenarios where computational budgets are severely constrained.

Relationship to PEFT Methods. While parameter-efficient fine-tuning methods such as LoRA [Hu et al., 2022] and BitFit [Zaken et al., 2022] have gained prominence in NLP, BN-only fine-tuning occupies a distinct niche in CNN-based vision. Unlike LoRA (which introduces additional low-rank matrices) or adapter modules [Mudrakarta et al., 2019] (which add bottleneck layers), BN-only fine-tuning requires *no architectural modifications*—it simply changes which existing parameters receive gradients. This zero-overhead property makes it particularly attractive for deployment pipelines where model architecture must remain unchanged.

6 Limitations and Future Work

Our study has several limitations that suggest directions for future work.

Single dataset. All experiments use a Stanford Dogs-based dataset. Generalization to other fine-grained benchmarks (CUB-200 Birds, Stanford Cars) and coarse-grained datasets (CIFAR-100, Food-101) remains to be verified.

Single architecture. We evaluate only ResNet-50. Extension to other BN-containing architectures (EfficientNet, ResNeXt) and architectures with alternative normalization (LayerNorm in Vision Transformers, GroupNorm) is an important direction.

Backbone dependence. Our positive results rely on a strong ImageNet-pretrained ResNet-50 backbone. In preliminary experiments with substantially weaker or less pretrained backbones, overall accuracy collapsed to the low teens, indicating that BN-only fine-tuning by itself is insufficient when the feature extractor is under-trained. Studying BN-only strategies under a broader range of backbone strengths is therefore an important direction for future work.

No cross-validation. We use a single 80/20 split. k -fold cross-validation or multiple random splits would strengthen statistical claims.

GPU memory estimation. Memory figures are estimated based on optimizer state size, not profiled. Precise memory profiling with tools such as `nvidia-smi` or TensorFlow Profiler would provide more reliable measurements.

Future directions include: (i) multi-dataset evaluation on additional fine-grained and coarse-grained benchmarks; (ii) systematic comparison across multiple BN-based CNN backbones (e.g., EfficientNet, ResNeXt) to better understand backbone dependence; (iii) extending the type-based fine-tuning perspective to other normalization schemes and architectures (e.g., LayerNorm-only or GroupNorm-only adaptation in Transformer-based vision models); (iv) theoretical analysis of the implicit regularization effect via PAC-Bayes or Rademacher complexity bounds.

7 Conclusion

BatchNorm-only fine-tuning has been explored in prior transfer learning literature as a parameter-efficient adaptation strategy. In this work, we systematically apply and evaluate this approach in a resource-constrained fine-grained classification setting—122-breed dog classification using a ResNet-50 backbone—to assess its practical viability beyond standard benchmarks. Our experiments show that training only BN layers and the classification head (4.7% of total parameters) achieves validation accuracy matching or slightly exceeding full fine-tuning (+0.10 pp), while reducing trainable parameters by 95.3%, training time by 33%, and estimated GPU memory by 62%. The strong implicit regularization effect—shrinking the train-validation gap from +23.7% to +0.6%—suggests that, at least in this setting, BN-only fine-tuning behaves not merely as a compression trick but as a practically robust adaptation strategy for practitioners operating under hardware constraints.

Acknowledgments

The author used AI writing assistance tools for language editing and figure generation scripts.

References

- Jia Deng, Wei Dong, Richard Socher, Li-Jia Li, Kai Li, and Li Fei-Fei. Imagenet: A large-scale hierarchical image database. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 248–255, 2009.
- Jonathan Frankle, David J. Schwab, and Ari S. Morcos. Training batchnorm and only batchnorm: On the expressive power of random features in cnns. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2021.
- Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 770–778, 2016.
- Edward J. Hu, Yelong Shen, Phillip Wallis, Zeyuan Allen-Zhu, Yuanzhi Li, Shean Wang, Lu Wang, and Weizhu Chen. Lora: Low-rank adaptation of large language models. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2022.
- Sergey Ioffe and Christian Szegedy. Batch normalization: Accelerating deep network training by reducing internal covariate shift. In *Proceedings of the 32nd International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, pages 448–456, 2015.
- Fahdi Kanavati and Masayuki Tsuneki. Partial transfusion: On the expressive influence of trainable batch norm parameters for transfer learning. In *Medical Imaging with Deep Learning (MIDL)*, pages 338–353. PMLR, 2021.
- Aditya Khosla, Nityananda Jayadevaprakash, Bangpeng Yao, and Fei-Fei Li. Novel dataset for fine-grained image categorization: Stanford dogs. In *Proceedings of the CVPR Workshop on Fine-Grained Visual Categorization (FGVC)*, 2011.
- Simon Kornblith, Jonathon Shlens, and Quoc V. Le. Do better imagenet models transfer better? In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 2661–2671, 2019.
- Yanhao Li, Naiyan Wang, Jianping Shi, Jiaying Liu, and Xiaodi Hou. Revisiting batch normalization for practical domain adaptation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1603.04779*, 2016.
- Pramod Kaushik Mudrakarta, Mark Sandler, Andrey Zhmoginov, and Andrew Howard. K for the price of 1: Parameter-efficient multi-task and transfer learning. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2019.
- Moslem Yazdanpanah, Aamer Abdul Rahman, Muawiz Chaudhary, Christian Desrosiers, Shreyas Bhatt, Maneesh Bhatt, Ahmed Ragab, and Samira Hashemi. Revisiting learnable affines for batch norm in few-shot transfer learning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 9099–9108, 2022.
- Elad Ben Zaken, Yoav Goldberg, and Shauli Ravfogel. Bitfit: Simple parameter-efficient fine-tuning for transformer-based masked language-models. *Proceedings of the 60th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*, pages 1–9, 2022.